

agro BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report

Responsible Partner: UNIMOS

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“Let’s meet!” Event Validation Report – Lithuania

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1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of **UNIMOS for the organisation and validation of the Producer Event in Lithuania on 6th and 13th March 2023**. These events were one of the four “Let’s meet!” event concepts designed in agroBRIDGES Task 3.4 for the local promotion of Short Food Supply Chains, locally produced food and involved market actors, namely (i) Producer Events, (ii) Culinary Events, (iii) Celebrate local heroes / SFSCs, and (iv) Open Days. The organisation, planning and implementation of the event was performed using the guidelines and templates designed by FBCD for each event concept to enable actors in the agri-food sector in replicating the events in their local agri-food ecosystems.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the Let’s meet event in Lithuania.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s meet!” event organisation details

2.1 Concept selection and definition of activities (programme)

Let’s meet events in Lithuania took place on 6th March 2023 and 13th March 2023 in the city of Vilnius – capital of Lithuania. Both of them were organized as a culinary event.

In order to implement them, several preparative activities took place that consisted of:

1. In-depth analysis of deliverables related to needs of Lithuanian stakeholders in terms of building SFSC
2. Consultations with local experts linked to selecting the best date, venue, format and programme that would address those needs and would be attractive to participants.
3. Preparation of materials and graphics to promote the event
4. Logistic organization of the events
5. Execution of the meeting and feedback gathering
6. Consultations after the organization of the meetings and lessons learned sharing session

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Short description	Date & Time (local)	Location
6th March 2023 – Let’s meet event in Lithuania # 1			
Activity #1	Presentation of agroBRIDGES project and its goals	11:00 - 11:30	Lithuanian Innovation Center (LIC) Mokslininkų g. 6A, 08412 Vilnius Lithuania
Activity #2	Degustation of local products in form of food catering based on common competences	11:30 - 12:00	
Activity #3	Discussion on how to build SFSC in Lithuania and how to finance it using portfolio of LIC’s projects, services and networks	12:00 - 12:30	
Activity #4	Networking among participants	12:30 - 13:00	
13th March 2023 – Let’s meet event in Lithuania # 2			
Activity #1	Presentation of agroBRIDGES project and its goals	12:00 - 12:30	Baltos Lankos Publishing House Gedimino, 28 LT-01104 Vilnius Lithuania
Activity #2	Degustation of local products in form of food catering based on common competences	12:30 - 13:00	
Activity #3	Discussion on how to build SFSC in Lithuania and how promote SFSC in cities	13:00 - 13:30	
Activity #4	Networking among participants	13:30 - 14:00	

2.2 Location, Venue/Space selection and arrangements

In order to select the location and venue, different options were considered, including organization of the “Let's meet!” event as a side event at bigger agriculture fair Ka pasesi 2023 in Kaunas that took place at the end of March 2023.

The organizers together with local Lithuanian experts jointly analysed the timeline, formal validation process requirements, the need to ensure the proper collection of documents and reporting deadlines. Taking this into account, they discussed the potential formats, models and attractiveness for participants, as well as Lithuanian market needs, expectations and logistic possibilities to organize the events.

Finally, it was agreed to organize two separate events with two different approaches to promoting SFSC in Lithuania.

The first meeting took place on March 6th, 2023 at the Lithuanian Innovation Center (LIC). The organization is aimed at increasing of Lithuanian international competitiveness by stimulating innovations in business and focuses on:

- fostering capabilities of the companies to develop and implement innovations,
- accelerating commercialization of achievements of advanced sciences and
- implementing Lithuanian innovation policy.

Figure 1: The Lithuanian Innovation Center (1st event location) - inside

LIC's headquarters is located in a business centre that is the office of more than 80 companies representing different sectors and industries.

Figure 2: The Lithuanian Innovation Center (1st event location) – outside

The second meeting took place on March 13th, 2023, at Publish Housing located at Gedimono Street. It is one of the main streets of Vilnius where not only the main Lithuanian governmental institutions -- like parliament, government, and ministries- are concentrated, but it is also a popular shopping, commercial and dining street. It is known as "Vilnius' 5th Avenue". The event was organized in a venue that serves for different purposes, including education, social integration activities and bookstore.

Figure 3: Publish Housings, Vilnius (2nd event location)

The first meeting took place on March 6th, 2023, at the Lithuanian Innovation Center (LIC). The organization is aimed at increasing of Lithuanian international competitiveness by stimulating innovations in business and focuses on:

- fostering capabilities of the companies to develop and implement innovations,
- accelerating commercialization of achievements of advanced sciences and
- implementing Lithuanian innovation policy.

LIC's headquarters is located in a business centre that is the office of more than 80 companies representing different sectors and industries.

The second meeting took place on March 13th, 2023, at Publish Housing located at Gedimono Street. It is one of the main streets of Vilnius where not only the main Lithuanian governmental institutions - like parliament, government, and ministries- are concentrated, but it is also popular shopping, commercial and dining street. It is known as "Vilnius' 5th Avenue". The event was organized in a venue that serves for different purposes, including education, social integration activities and bookstore.

2.3 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

In order to implement the event, both in-house and external personnel were involved to ensure technical and logistical smooth organization of the event.

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Graphic designers	1	Development of promo material	In-house	2 person days
Catering	4	Food and drinks for guests	External	N/A
Facilitators	2	Facilitation of the meeting	In-house and external	N/A

2.4 Event material

In order to promote the events, several materials have been prepared. Dedicated post for social media in Lithuanian was prepared and posted on LinkedIn platform with the invitation to participate in two events in Vilnius.

It was printed and put in the venue for informative purposes. In the first meeting, a list of local producers was prepared to showcase their products. In the second meeting a poster was printed to invite general public. Additionally, two power point master slides were prepared.

Figure 4: Graphic materials for printing, posting and presenting

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Susitikime!

Let's meet! LIETUVA

**Susitikime degustuojant vietinius produktus ir aptarkime,
kaip kurti trumpas maisto produktų tiekimo grandines (SFSC)!**

KULINARINIS RENGINYS

6 kovo 2023 - 11.00

Lietuvos inovacijų centras

Projektas finansuojamas pagal ES mokslinių tyrimų ir inovacijų programą „Horizontas 2020“, dotacijos sutarties Nr. 101000788.

UNIMOS
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BRIDGES

Susitikime!

Let's meet! LIETUVA

**Susitikime degustuojant vietinius produktus ir aptarkime,
kaip kurti trumpas maisto produktų tiekimo grandines (SFSC)!**

KULINARINIS RENGINYS

13 kovo 2023 - 12.00

Gedimino pr. 28, Vilnius

Projektas finansuojamas pagal ES mokslinių tyrimų ir inovacijų programą „Horizontas 2020“, dotacijos sutarties Nr. 101000788.

2.5 Engagement of contributors and collaborators

The concept of producer event was selected to connect SFSC products and producers with important stakeholders who can support them not only as potential customers, but also as partners who can indicate business, collaboration and projects opportunities to finance SFSC initiatives and individual business. To do so, collaboration with strategic partner - Lithuanian Innovation Center (LIC) - was established.

The second meeting was organized in the main street of Vilnius and in a venue that combines social, economic, and educative purposes. The selection of the place was in line with the results of agroBRIDGES co-creation workshop in Lithuania where the importance of SFSC social benefits and their economic and environmental impacts were highlighted as important factor of development of SFSC in this Baltic country.

The organization of the events started in February 2023 with the selection of the dates, venues and formats that are most suitable to Lithuanian local needs and would fulfil agroBRIDGES needs. Continuous consultations regarding the holistic organization have been taking place since mid-February 2023.

2.6 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

The engagement and promotional strategy for reaching out to broader audience were mainly done by direct contacts and were supported by social media posts. The engagement campaign started approximately 3 weeks before the events.

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

Two Let's meet events were organized and were divided into five synergic sections.

The first Let's meet event was held on 6th March 2023 at LIC premises. It started with the welcome speech, information about agroBRIDGES projects, its goals and presentation of degustation concept based on SFSC approach.

The food/recipes offered to guests included the Lithuanian traditional products, such as:

- Duonos gira- Lithuanian kvass - traditional Lithuanian drink made from fermented dark rye bread, often served in Lithuania as a summertime drink
- Lithuanian šakotis "tree cake" - a cake cooked on a rotating spit in an oven or over an open fire
- herpring with pickled cucumbers in form of small canapés
- traditional cheeses, cold meat and sausages
- bread, sticks and veggies

The degustation of local foods triggered discussion between participants about SFSC, possibilities of boosting special dietary options (vegan, vegetarian, etc.) and how to reinvent regional and traditional products in new, fusion and fine versions. For instance, guests shared ideas about the creation of new culinary tapas and finger foods experiences by mixing Lithuanian products with unusual, novel or international ingredients to boost food innovations. Questions related to the availability of financial and technical support to make it happen arose, highlighting the need to have external facilitation to coordinate and orchestrate this kind of action. Lithuanian Innovation Center (LIC) innovation projects portfolio and support services were discussed, especially in terms of ongoing EU-projects where potential synergies could be created.

The second event was held on 13th March 2023 at Publishing House Baltos Lankos and started with the presentation of agroBRIDGES project and its goals.

Attendees were invited to taste food products in the form of snack catering based on local products. The concept resulted to be very interesting for Lithuanian consumers, as it was a new, fresh and creative combination of traditional food, but presented in novel finger foods format. Creating unusual experiences using regional and traditional products was appreciated and guests discussed ideas on how to build SFSC in Lithuania with specific focus on the promotion of SFSC in popular city locations such as Gedimono Street ("Vilnius 5th Avenue"). Special attention was put on restaurants (for instance, SFSC products in menus or thematic days) and on SFSC food related activities to build relations, brand recognition and to attract clients / visitors to visit shops and commercial locals. Additionally, new food experiences creation was thought as a new way of urban entertainment that combines education, health and local business promotion.

Figure 5: Pictures from the events in Lithuania

3.2 Event participation

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Producers	6
Consumers	45
Total	51

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event concept by participants

Let's meet event on 6th March 2023

Question	Yes		No		Not sure	
Question #1: Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event	24		3		4	
Question	Absolutely agree	Agree	Do not agree or disagree	Disagree	Fully Disagree	No answer
Question #2: Did you find this event informative about new/unknown types of food produced in your region?	13	17	0	0	0	1
Question #3: Did you find this event helpful for getting to know local food businesses, restaurants, their methods and efforts to bring local food closer to you?	14	17	0	0	0	0
Question #4: Did you find the activities organised helpful to understand the value of local food, local recipes and their various benefits for your health, the environment, and the society?	21	10	0	0	0	0
Question #5: Did you find enough information about how and where to find the local restaurants and kitchens and other hospitality businesses you've met?	17	14	0	0	0	0
Question	Monthly or more often	3-4 times a year	Twice a year	Once a year	Never	I prefer not to answer
Question #6: Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region? How often?	13	11	7	0	0	0

Let's meet event on 13th March 2023

Question	Yes		No		Not sure	
Question #1: Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event	10		10		0	
Question	Absolutely agree	Agree	Do not agree or disagree	Disagree	Fully Disagree	No answer
Question #2: Did you find this event informative about new/unknown types of food produced in your region?	12	5	0	0	0	3
Question #3: Did you find this event helpful for getting to know local food businesses, restaurants, their methods and efforts to bring local food closer to you?	12	7	0	0	0	1
Question #4: Did you find the activities organised helpful to understand the value of local food, local recipes and their various benefits for your health, the environment, and the society?	12	6	0	0	0	2
Question #5: Did you find enough information about how and where to find the local restaurants and kitchens and other hospitality businesses you've met?	13	6	1	0	0	0
Question	Monthly or more often	3-4 times a year	Twice a year	Once a year	Never	I prefer not to answer
Question #6: Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region? How often?	2	5	6	7	0	0

4.1.2 Validation of “Let’s meet!” guidelines and templates by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event concepts relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

The event concepts are relevant to Lithuanian local agri-food ecosystems and different organizations. UNIMOS as Beacon Leader of Lithuania region was responsible for the organization of Let’s meet events in Lithuania. Its effective organization was based on close collaboration with Lithuanian local and native experts, continuous contacts to explain agroBRIDGES tools, mutual openness and learning orientation towards Lithuanian market. In the future, more events like this should be organized, especially those that create new food combinations based on common competences of individual products with novel aspects, shapes and textures and addressing different dietary needs.

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments?

Yes, definitely we would organize the same event again in Lithuania. In terms of potential improvements, we would consider including different dietary options (for instance, vegan), as well as degustation of novel, unusual food products and their combinations.

Question #3: Did you find the guidelines and templates sufficient for your event organization needs?

All the materials provided were useful and very practical. Its translation into Lithuanian speeded up the organization and promotion of the events, allowing its replication and adaptation.

Question #4: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines accurate enough to plan effectively?

The instructions of the guidelines were accurate enough to plan effectively and organize two meetings in Lithuania.

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Yes, because two events were organized in Lithuania with two different ways to promote SFSC. The guidelines served as inspiration allowing flexibility to adjust the concepts of the event to local ecosystems, business needs and audiences.

4.1.3 *Limitations and barriers of the organising partner*

As the agri-food sector is highly dynamic and customer expectations are constantly shifting, attention should be paid to design experiences and address consumer demands. For instance, there is a growing vegan trend in Lithuania and vegan options in menus would have addressed expectations of plant-based eating and vegan customers. This is why continuous market research and meeting consumer demand for both meat and meat-free products could be considered for future organization of SFSC events.

4.1.4 *Suggestions for improvement of the concept and guidelines*

Question #5: Did you find the instructions of the guidelines flexible enough to create an event tailored to your ecosystem/business needs?

Yes, the instructions of the guidelines were flexible enough to create two different events tailored to different needs and both were successfully implemented. It is a “ready to use” set of tools that can be easily adapted to different types of events organized by public, private and non-governmental organizations.

5. Conclusions

Two Let’s meet events in Lithuania were a very good opportunity to create a space for networking and interconnections between Lithuanian customers, producers and innovation support stakeholders. Joint tasting of SFSC products triggered promotion and discussion about novel ways of creation exceptional food customer experiences that Lithuanian customers would be interested in. There is a room for experimentation and design of new food combinations, also at cross-border level and with the engagement of food producers from other European countries. As the financing support is one of the main issues to support building SFSC in Lithuania, direct contact with stakeholders working on innovation support is one of the ways to support opening new possibilities for development, financing of innovations and accessing new markets.